

Applications of Stellarium Software: A Review

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A planetarium software is a software allowing users to simulate the celestial sphere according to a given time and location. Software can simply display a star chart or, with increasing complexity, can give to the observer a photorealistic rendering of the sky. Here we will consider the Stellarium Planetarium and its applications in several studies.

Stellarium is an open-source free-software planetarium, having GNU General Public License. It is available for Linux, Windows, and macOS. Stellarium Mobile is also available for Android, iOS, and Symbian. In all the versions, Stellarium uses OpenGL to render a realistic projection of the night sky in real time, according to the system requirements given at the web site stellarium.org. The most recent guide of this software is available [1].

Figure 1 - A screenshot from the web page stellarium.org.

MEDIA INAF is proposing the software in [2]. "Stellarium. Questo programma, un vero e proprio "simulatore di cielo", è totalmente gratuito." Besides a wide catalog of stars, "Nel programma sono ovviamente presenti e visualizzabili tutti i pianeti del Sistema solare, gran parte delle loro lune, la rappresentazione fotorealistica della Via Lattea, oltre a centinaia di nebulose e galassie. Il tutto presentato con un'interfaccia

molto intuitiva e anche in lingua italiana."

In MEDIA INAF, in article [3], we can find a first application of Stellarium, the analysis of the astronomical references in Dante's Divine Comedy, as proposed by Nicola Iannelli, author of [4].

Several applications of Stellarium.

"The Virtual Astronomy Multimedia Project (VAMP) and the Astronomy Visualization Metadata (AVM) standard will give observatories and astronomers an easy way to distribute their astronomical visualisation products". In Ref.[5], applications like Stellarium, World Wide Telescope, and Sky in Google Earth were considered.

In [6] - [15] we can find Stellarium proposed and used for the education of young people in astronomy. Stellarium is clearly appreciated for the ease of use. Article [12] lists "some ideas for using the software [Stellarium] to address goals and focus areas of the International Year of Astronomy 2009. Stellarium can help astronomy educators reach many of the goals of IYA2009".

Abstract of [16] tells that "the skyscape is an important method for developing meaning in the context of archaeoastronomical findings. In some cases the appearance of the sky needs to be simulated to reproduce conditions as they would have been experienced during the time period of interest". This is requiring a good planetarium software, such as Stellarium. Stellarium is also offering a "representative dimension towards an artistic tool to convey mood and capture emotion".

Ref. [17] is concerning how "The old adapts to the modern: checking the Astronomical Unity value by reproducing the Venus transit with the Stellarium software",

Several examples of the use of Stellarium have been given in [18] for simulating the astronomical landscapes of the ancient stargazers. The focus was on the motion of the stars, in particular with respect to the precession of Equinoxes. In [19], Stellarium software is used for simulating a phenomenon of 1497, the lunar occultation of Aldebaran observed by Nicolaus Copernicus. In [19], CalSKY software has been also used for the phase of the moon [20].

Ref. [21] is also proposing Stellarium for an astrophysical virtual laboratory for teaching purposes. Ref.[22] tells that Stellarium, "Apart from visualizing the seemingly perpetual regular motions of the celestial bodies, it can be used to visualize and demonstrate historical solar and lunar eclipses, historical and present comets, meteors, and also novae and supernovae".

Abstract of [23] begins telling that planetarium Stellarium gained high popularity for simulation in archaeoastronomy. "A dedicated plugin which we introduced a few years ago can be used to visualize loadable scenes of 3D reconstructions of past or present monuments in their landscape." The novelty in [23] is the proposal of an application which is enabling "the simulation of phased or temporally evolving three-dimensional

sceneries under Stellarium's sky by configuring parts of the 3D model with material properties that can be used to hide parts of the monument when they don't fit the epoch of the currently simulated sky".

In [24], authors tell that Stellarium is used "for research and dissemination of results in Cultural Astronomy". LBI ArchPro and TU Wien "have added significant capabilities for applications in Cultural Astronomy to the program, in particular a way to allow virtual 3D exploration of architecture from any period".

Authors of [25] present the development of a virtual spacecraft simulator game. "The project utilises various open source hardware and software platforms including Stellarium, Raspberry Pi, HappyBrackets and the Azul Zulu Java Virtual Machine".

Ref. [26] has the following abstract: "The study of the bases of spherical astronomy and astrometry is very important for the right understanding of the phenomena and their conformity as well as it also enables to explain them. But this topics doesn't seem to be interesting and neither well understood to the students". The authors have developed the demonstrations with the use of virtual planetarium Stellarium too.

In [27], it is told that "educators are called to favor digital literacy, introducing the different technological tools for educational purposes since they are part of the daily use of children. Augmented reality and the Stellarium program are powerful tools for teaching astronomy, since they allow observing the stars, constellations and solar system, facilitating the explanation of celestial phenomena to the educator". Also [28] - [34] are discussing the use of Stellarium for teaching purposes.

As we have seen, many articles are devoted to the use of Stellarium for helping students in the comprehension of astronomy. However, we can use the software for simulation of ancient astronomical events for historical, chronological and, as previously told, archaeoastronomical studies.

Ref. [35] simulated the sky as seen by Tycho. "SN 1572, also known as the Tycho's Nova, was a supernova largely reported and discussed in the literature of the time". Ref. [35] talks about this literature. In the latest texts, we can find also mentioned the Kepler's Nova, today known as SN 1604, and other newly observed stars.

The use of Stellarium and Photographer's Ephemeris software is proposed in [36] to test a possible astronomical orientation of the Great Enclosure of Musawwarat es Sufra, in the heartland of the Kingdom of Kush. Other archaeoastronomical applications, concerning the Roman Towns, are available in [37] and [38]. [37] is proposing the study of the orientation of the Roman Colonia Marciana Ulpia Traiana Thamugadi (Timgad in Algeria), founded in 100 AD. In [38] Novaesium is considered. The town was a Roman fort on the Rhine, a fort which served for the campaigns of Augustus and Drusus against Germans. The plan is the standard one of the Roman camps.

In [39], it is the Avenue of Sphinxes, a 2.8 kilometres long Avenue linking Luxor and Karnak temples, which is considered for archaeoastronomy. This avenue was the processional road of the Opet Festival from the Karnak temple to the Luxor temple and

the Nile. It seems that direction of the rising of Vega was probably used as reference direction for the surveying. In the Figure 2, the setting of the Crux at Luxor, 1290 BC.

Figure2 - Setting of the Crux, 1290 BC, Luxor, as shown by Stellarium [39].

Figure 3 - "Il sorgere di Orione nel 550 BC visto da Stoccarda simulato con Stellarium, riferimento azimutale. L'orizzonte astronomico è mostrato dalla linea blu" [43]

Alpha Crucis was the subject of [40]. The paper is proposing a possible link between the construction of the Silbury Hill, the prehistoric artificial mound near Avebury, and the observation of the main star of the Crux constellation, which was slowly

disappearing from the local sky due to the precession of the Earth's axis. For the discussion, simulations of the local astronomical landscape, made by means of Stellarium software, were used.

Other examples of the use of this software for archaeoastronomical studies are available in [41] - [45]. Figure 3 is from [43].

Stellarium and Chronology - Software Stellarium and CalSKY have been used for chronology in [46] and [47]. Eclipses were investigated. In [46] we considered the **eclipses** mentioned by Titus Livius (Livy) in his monumental history of Rome, entitled *Ab Urbe Condita Libri*. For two of these eclipses, Livy is also reporting the dates. Therefore, these eclipses are fundamental for the Roman chronology. In [47], we proposed an archaeoastronomical discussion of evidence concerning the dating of the Battle of Gaugamela. This battle was preceded by a total lunar eclipse, which is also known as the eclipse of Alexander, used to date the decisive battle of the invasion of the Persian Achaemenid Empire.

Figure 4 - "L'immagine è la simulazione da Leida al 27 Luglio 1753" [48]. Occultation of Venus by the Moon, 27 July 1753, Leiden. This occultation is reported by astronomers.

Occultation of stars and planets - For what concerns the history of astronomy, we have already proposed [19], where the occultation of Aldebaran observed by Copernicus was studied. Other case studies are mentioned in [48]. "In precedenza si era studiata con Stellarium l'occultazione di Aldebaran da parte della Luna, osservata e riportata da Copernico nel 1497. Nel caso di questo fenomeno, la luna è all'apparenza molto più grande della stella. Vediamo ora come si comporta il software nel caso di diametri apparenti più piccoli". "Le analisi svolte dimostrano che l'eccellente software Stellarium riproduce perfettamente gli eventi storici riportati da grandi astronomi del passato.

Come già detto in [20] per il software CalSKY, Stellarium è perfetto per analisi archeoastronomiche. Non è quindi necessario che chi si accinge a svolgere uno studio archeoastronomico crei un software specifico per l'analisi. Stellarium, fornendo il cielo stellato ed i dati relativi, è utilizzabile allo scopo". It is not necessary that researchers, who are preparing themselves to carry out an archaeoastronomic study, create specific software for the analysis. Stellarium, providing the starry sky and related data, can be used for this purpose.

"[Stellarium is] much more than a simple star chart — it's a serious astronomy tool rich with viewing options and information about celestial objects. It's very popular in the astronomical community. We use it at the space centre for our "Night Sky Viewer" interactive display. At the local observatory where I work, it's used for public presentations as well as to plan telescope sessions and even control telescopes. It's popular with both amateur and professional astronomers." Dave Owen, Feb 2018, Te Awamutu Space Centre.

Venus and the Moon - The Figure 4 is showing the occultation of Venus by the Moon, 27 July 1753, Leiden, as simulated by means of Stellarium. This occultation is reported by astronomers. Now, let us consider the occultation of Venus by the Moon, AD554, October 9, discussed in [49]. In this reference, we can find the times of the phenomena given in UT. The beginning of the occultation (immersion) is given as the moment when the limb of the Moon touches the planet. For all the calculations the authors of [49] used VSOP87 theory.

Data provided in [49] for the occultation of Venus by the Moon, that we use for a simulation by means of Stellarium, are the date, October 9, 554, the place, Metz 49°07'N, 6°10'E, the beginning of occultation 5h16m 6. The historical medieval source is not giving date and time but a description that authors of [49] have discussed in detail. The primary source is Gregory of Tours who stated that: "In his time, we saw grapes grow on the tree we call saucum without having any vine on it, and the blossoms of the same trees (...) Then a star coming from the opposite direction was seen to enter the disk of the fifth Moon. I suppose these signs announced the death of the king" (see please the detailed discussion in [49]). Let us compare the occultation given in [49] and the Stellarium. Figure 5 is obtained from Stellarium screenshots. The method for the planets is the same; however, we can stress that results are in excellent agreement.

Let us note that Stellarium contains implementations of VSOP87 [50] and ELP82B [51], and Vondrak2011 for precession [52].

Figure 5. Metz, 554, October 9.

In the following Figure 6, we can see the data collected from a simulation obtained by means of Stellarium, of the occultation of Venus by the Moon, observed by Abraham Zacut in 1476, the 24 of July. Calculation in [53] tells that occultation began 8:43h after true noon. Stellarium has the application to obtain the equation of time, but it is also possible to observe the local noon.

Figure 6. Salamanca (Castille and Leon), 1476, July 24.

Mars and the Moon - In the Figure 7 we can find the occultation of Mars by the Moon, simulated by Stellarium, as seen from Athens. This occultation is discussed in [54]. "In his *De caelo*, Aristotle cites an observation that he made of the occultation of planet Mars by the Moon. ... "For we have seen the Moon, half full, pass beneath the planet Mars, which vanished on its shadow side and came forth by the bright and shining part". No hint of the date when this event occurred is given by Aristotle." [54].

"Attempts to date this observation by astronomical calculation originated with Kepler" [54]. It was in 1927 that Carl Schoch emended the date proposed by Kepler to 4 May 357 BC.

Figure 7. Athens, 357 BC (-356 in Stellarium), May 4. Moon illuminated 44.2%.

Conclusion

Here we have proposed a review of scholar literature about the use of Stellarium [55], for teaching purposes, archaeoastronomical and chronological analyses. We have also shown simulations of the occultation of Venus by the Moon and of Mars by the Moon.

Comparison with literature provides an excellent agreement.

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